

Hydroxylamine Hydrochloride as a Complexing Agent in the Separation of Cations using Cation and Anion Exchange Chromatography

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The ion exchange studies using ammonium salts were reported¹. A comparative study of distribution coefficients, from which the most favourable eluent concentrations can be estimated directly and which enables an evaluation and comparison of various eluting agents has been reported by Strelow and Weinert². Other reports³ show no systematic information about cation and anion exchange selectivity of metal ions used in $\text{NH}_2\text{OH.HCl}$. Hence it was thought to be of interest to investigate the ion exchange characterisation of a number of cations in $\text{NH}_2\text{OH.HCl}$ medium using cation exchanger Dowex 50 W-X-8 in H^+ -form and anion exchanger Dowex 1-X-8 in Cl^- -form. All the elements were tested separately at various molar concentrations of $\text{NH}_2\text{OH.HCl}$ ($0.2\text{--}1.2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$).

Results and Discussion

The values of distribution coefficient (k) in cation exchange show that with increasing amounts of $\text{NH}_2\text{OH.HCl}$ there is a decrease in values of k of all the metal ions examined. Though this extent of decrease varies with the metal ions. Therefore, in cation exchange the presence of $\text{NH}_2\text{OH.HCl}$ reduces the affinity of all the metal ions towards the cation exchanger due to formation of complex with amine and chloride groups. Whereas in anion exchange, the investigated elements may be divided into following two groups with regard to their adsorption characteristics : (i) no adsorption and (ii) strong adsorption.

No adsorption : This contains the elements with

very low values of distribution coefficients at all the concentrations of hydroxyl amine hydrochloride. Mg^{II} , Al^{III} , Ca^{II} , Cr^{III} , Sr^{II} , Y^{III} , Sc^{III} , Ba^{II} , La^{III} , Ce^{III} , Pr^{III} and Gd^{III} do not form anionic complex with $\text{NH}_2\text{OH.HCl}$, therefore, they are not retained by anion exchanger and have low k values at all the concentrations of $\text{NH}_2\text{OH.HCl}$. These metal ions can be separated from other metal ions, viz. Fe^{III} , In^{III} , Hg^{II} , Zn^{II} etc. having high k values.

Strong adsorption : To this class belong Fe^{III} , Zn^{II} , Hg^{II} and In^{III} . In all cases the adsorption increases with increasing $\text{NH}_2\text{OH.HCl}$ concentrations due to formation of strong anionic complex. In cation exchange a remarkable decrease in k values of Hg^{II} was observed in all media. This anomalous behaviour is due to strong complexing tendency of Hg^{II} with $\text{NH}_2\text{OH.HCl}$. Therefore, Hg^{II} can be separated from other cations at lower concentration (0.2 mol dm^{-3}) of $\text{NH}_2\text{OH.HCl}$. In cation exchange at higher concentrations of $\text{NH}_2\text{OH.HCl}$ ($1.0\text{--}1.2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$), k values of La^{III} , Ce^{III} , Y^{III} , Pr^{III} , Gd^{III} and Sc^{III} are higher than other metal ions. Therefore these metal ions can be separated from their binary mixtures with other metal ions, viz. In^{III} , Fe^{III} , Al^{III} and Cr^{III} .

Chromatographic separation in cation exchanger : Fully water-swollen cation exchanger Dowex 50 W-X-8 (H^+ -form; 100-200 mesh) was transferred to a glass column ($65 \text{ cm} \times 0.85 \text{ cm}$ dia) and height of the resin column was kept 8 cm. The feed (25 cm^3) of $\text{NH}_2\text{OH.HCl}$ (0.2 mol dm^{-3}) prepared by mixing aliquots of standard solu-

tions of metal, was passed through the column; the flow rate being maintained at $1.0 \pm 0.3 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$. The effluent was collected in 5 cm^3 fractions from the beginning of sorption step. After the sorption step the column was washed with $0.2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ NH}_2\text{OH.HCl}$, collecting the effluent in 5 cm^3 fractions. Fresh eluent was used for eluting the strongly retained metal ions.

Binary separations :

Hg^{II} from other metal ions : The feed was prepared by mixing an aliquot of standard solution of Hg^{II} and one of the other metal ions to be separated in $\text{NH}_2\text{OH.HCl}$ (0.2 mol dm^{-3}). The mixture was passed through the resin bed at a flow rate of $1.0 \pm 0.3 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$. Hg^{II} passed into the feed effluent while other metal ions were sorbed on resin bed. The column with sorbed cations was washed with $0.2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ NH}_2\text{OH.HCl}$ ($40\text{--}50 \text{ cm}^3$). The total eluent volume (25 cm^3 feed + 40 cm^3 washing solution) was found to be sufficient for quantitative recovery of Hg^{II} . Other metal ions Mn^{II} , Ca^{II} , Sr^{II} , Ba^{II} , Fe^{III} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} , Al^{III} or In^{III} were then eluted with $\text{NH}_2\text{OH.HCl}$ (1.2 mol dm^{-3}).

La^{III}, Ce^{III}, Y^{III}, Pr^{III}, Gd^{III} or Sc^{III} from other metal ions : The feed (25 cm^3) of $1.2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ NH}_2\text{OH.HCl}$ was prepared by mixing standard solutions of one of the most strongly retained elements (e.g. La^{III} , Ce^{III} , Y^{III} , Pr^{III} , Gd^{III} or Sc^{III}) and one of the weakly sorbed elements. After washing the column, weakly sorbed elements were eluted with $1.2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ NH}_2\text{OH.HCl}$. The strongly retained elements were desorbed with $3 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ HNO}_3$.

Ternary separations : The feed (25 cm^3) of $0.2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ NH}_2\text{OH.HCl}$ was prepared by mixing the solutions of (i) Hg^{II} , (ii) $\text{Mg}^{\text{II}} / \text{Ca}^{\text{II}} / \text{Sr}^{\text{II}} / \text{Ba}^{\text{II}} / \text{Fe}^{\text{III}} / \text{Co}^{\text{II}} / \text{Ni}^{\text{II}} / \text{Cu}^{\text{II}} / \text{Zn}^{\text{II}}$, $\text{Cd}^{\text{II}} / \text{Al}^{\text{III}} / \text{Cr}^{\text{III}}$ or In^{III} and (iii) $\text{La}^{\text{III}} / \text{Ce}^{\text{III}} / \text{Y}^{\text{III}} / \text{Pr}^{\text{III}} / \text{Gd}^{\text{III}}$ or Sc^{III} . First, Hg^{II} was eluted with $0.2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ NH}_2\text{OH.HCl}$, then weakly sorbed elements with $1.2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ NH}_2\text{OH.HCl}$, followed by strongly sorbed elements with $3 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ HNO}_3$. The results are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—QUANTITATIVE SEPARATION OF SYNTHETIC MIXTURE

Found/(Taken) (μg)			
Hg^{II}	Ce^{III}	Other	
94 42	62.70	Cu^{II}	32 30
(94 23)	62 50		32 06)
94 32	62 55	Cd^{II}	53 85
(94 23)	62.50		53 95)
94 30	62 50	Cd^{II}	77 62
(94 23)	62 50		77 80)
94 40	62 85	Fe^{III}	27 92
(94 23)	62 50		27 90)
94 20	62 65	Al^{III}	13 50
(94 23)	62 50		13 45)
94 25	62 82	Cr^{III}	25 28
(94 23)	62 50		25 16)
Hg^{II}	La^{III}	Other	
94 38	58 82	Cu^{II}	32 32
(94 35)	58 88		32 06)
94 32	58 88	Cd^{II}	53 93
(94 35)	58 87		53.90)
94 39	58 66	Cd^{II}	17 78
(94 35)	58 87		17 80)
94 40	58 90	Fe^{III}	26 68
(94 35)	58 87		26 70)
94 28	58 92	Al^{III}	13.50
(94 35)	58.87		13 45)
94 30	58 88	Cr^{III}	26 30
(94 35)	58 87		26 23)
Hg^{II}	In^{III}	Other	
95 30	38 09	Sc^{III}	20.93
(95 28)	37.52		20 82)
95 28	37 83	Y^{III}	43 15
(95 28)	37 52		42 60)
95 28	37 62	Pr^{III}	68 70
(95 28)	37 52		68 72)
95 27	37 74	Gd^{III}	70 88
(95 28)	37 52		70 85)

Chromatographic separation in anion exchanger :

Separation of $\text{Fe}^{\text{III}} / \text{Hg}^{\text{II}} / \text{Zn}^{\text{II}}$ or In^{III} from other cations : The feed was prepared by mixing standard solution of $\text{Fe}^{\text{III}} / \text{Hg}^{\text{II}} / \text{Zn}^{\text{II}}$ or In^{III} and one of the other metal ions to be separated, in $1.2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ NH}_2\text{OH.HCl}$. $\text{Fe}^{\text{III}} / \text{Hg}^{\text{II}} / \text{Zn}^{\text{II}}$ or In^{III} were strongly retained on the resin. The other metal ions accompanied the feed effluent and were subsequently eluted by continuing the elution with $1.2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ NH}_2\text{OH.HCl}$. The metal ions strongly retained on the resin, were eluted with $3\text{--}5 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ HCl}$. In^{III} was eluted with $3 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ HCl}$ (120 cm^3) while Hg^{II} was eluted with $4 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ HCl}$ (160 cm^3). Fe^{III} was eluted with $3 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ HCl}$ (110 cm^3) and Zn^{II} with $3 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ HCl}$ (120 cm^3). The results are given in Table 2.

NOTE

TABLE 2—SEPARATION OF In^{III}/Hg^{II}/Fe^{III} FROM OTHER METALS

Amount (mg) : Found/(Taken)							
In ^{III}	Other	Hg ^{II}	Other	Fe ^{II}	Other	Co ^{II}	Other
56.20	Al ^{III} 12.62	98.02	Mn ^{II} 26.24	25.82		Co ^{II} 12.75	
(56.10)	12.60)	(98.00)	26.32)	(25.80)		12.80)	
56.22	Sc ^{III} 18.44	98.02	Co ^{II} 21.75	25.82		Ni ^{II} 24.00	
(56.10)	18.40)	(98.12)	21.78)	(25.85)		24.08)	
56.00	Mn ^{II} 24.86	98.02	Ni ^{II} 21.84	25.82		Sc ^{III} 18.40	
(56.10)	24.80)	(98.07)	21.76)	(25.86)		18.44)	
56.30	Co ^{II} 12.82	98.02	Cd ^{II} 56.62	25.82		Y ^{III} 41.00	
(56.25)	12.75)	(98.05)	56.65)	(25.84)		41.05)	
56.32	Ni ^{II} 24.95	98.02	Cr ^{III} 21.27				
(56.25)	24.94)	(98.10)	21.30)				
56.28	Y ^{III} 41.05						
(56.25)	41.00)						
56.29	Pr ^{III} 65.69						
(56.25)	65.72)						

Experimental

Cation exchange resin (H⁺-form) Dowex 50 W-X-8 sulphonate polystyrene (100–200 mesh) and anion exchange resin (Cl⁻-form) Dowex-1-X-8 (20–50 mesh) were used. Stock solutions of metal ions were prepared in water from their nitrates (A.R., B.D.H., Johnson Matthey). A 2.0 mol dm⁻³ stock solution of NH₂OH.HCl (E. Merck, G.R.) was prepared in water.

A batch equilibration method was employed for determining the distribution coefficients. All the experiments were performed at 30±2°.

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